

ASSOCIATION OF ACNE WITH FACE MASK USAGE IN PATIENTS PRESENTING IN THE OUTPATIENT DEPARTMENT AMIDST THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN LAHORE, PAKISTAN

Eilaf Azeem^{*1}, Ayesha Liaquat², Saleha Azeem³, Ghazala Butt⁴, Sumara Rashid⁵

^{*1}Student, International School Lahore, Lahore, Pakistan

²Dow Medical College, Lahore, Pakistan

³King Edward Medical University, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology, Shalamar Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

⁵Associate Professor, Department of Dermatology, Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

*eilafazeem2007@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Eilaf Azeem

Abstract

Background: Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, standard operating procedures such as mask usage have been set into place. They limit the transfer of infectious droplets and prevent contraction of the disease. They however, also create a hot and humid environment that blocks pilosebaceous units leading to acne. This study aimed to assess the association of acne with different factors of face mask usage in patients presenting to the OPD.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted in Mayo Hospital and Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. The questionnaire had three parts dealing with socio-demographic factors, details of facemask usage and details of acne respectively. Responses were collected and compiled into a written questionnaire, and the data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0.

Results: Among 204 respondents, 86.8% were female. 106 (51.9%) patients observed an increase in acne severity and 98 (48%) patients observed a decreased/constant state of acne severity. Type of facemask used and treatment for acne were significantly associated with acne severity ($p < 0.05$). No other variable including duration of mask usage, frequency of mask changing, skin type, use of comedogenic products, or frequency of face washing yielded significant results.

Conclusion: Our study suggests that acne severity increases with the use of stronger masks such as N-95 and KN-95 as compared to cloth and surgical masks. This could contribute to the development of targeted interventions aimed at minimizing the risk of acne onset and flares in the general population.

INTRODUCTION

The coronavirus pandemic, which originated in 2019 in Wuhan, China, spread across the globe rapidly. It was declared a public health emergency of international concern (PHEIC) by the World Health Organization (WHO) on January 30, 2020. Pakistan observed its first case of COVID-19 on February 26, 2020 in Karachi

COVID-19 is a highly contagious disease, with a significant mortality rate of 0.02% in Pakistan². It is primarily transmitted through respiratory droplets generated by speaking, coughing and sneezing. As a result, the use of masks was arguably the most stressed upon component of the standard operating procedures (SOPs) which

were devised by the Centre of Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) to contain the spread of the virus. However, the long-term use of face masks can potentially lead to adverse physical effects such as headaches, impaired cognition, skin breakdown, and rashes³. Similarly, it also increases the incidence and severity of acne vulgaris as proved by previous studies^{4,5}.

Acne vulgaris, the most common inflammatory dermatosis all over the world⁶, is a multifactorial disorder caused by the obstruction or inflammation of the pilosebaceous units due to the presence of bacteria, oil, or dead skin cells. It primarily affects the face, neck, shoulders, arms, chest and back. Other factors such as hormonal imbalances, stress and diet are known to affect this disease⁷. Likewise, wearing face masks for extended periods of time creates a hot and humid environment that can block facial ducts, leading to an acne flare³.

The objective of this research is to study the association of acne with facemask usage in patients presenting in the outpatient department of two tertiary care hospitals in Lahore. A similar study on healthcare workers has been previously carried out in Karachi, Pakistan.

Methods

This study was carried out from May to July 2022 in two hospitals: Mayo Hospital and Fatima Memorial Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan. The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board, King Edward Medical University (Reference number: 505/RC/KEMU). All patients presenting with acne to the outpatient department (OPD) in these two tertiary care hospitals and who had a history of wearing face masks were invited to participate in the study. The participants were informed of the purpose of the questionnaire and their written consent was taken prior to getting the questionnaire filled. Parents or guardians provided consent for any minors that took part in the study. Confidentiality and anonymity were thoroughly ensured and no names or email addresses were asked. All social and ethical considerations were given due care and importance. A total of 204 responses were collected.

The questionnaire was built from close-ended questions. It was developed using MS Word, with a consent form attached to it. Physical copies of the questionnaire were printed for the purpose of data collection. It was developed based on a literature review and previously published studies on mask-induced acne (maskne).

The questionnaire had several sections. The first section dealt with demographic variables such as age, gender, and marital status. The second section dealt with different factors related to mask usage. This included the type of mask they wore, the duration they wore it for daily, and the frequency with which they changed their mask. In case a patient used more than one mask, the stronger out of the two was marked. Strength of masks in increasing order was taken as cloth, surgical, KN-95, and N-95^{9,10}. Other questions such as skin type, the use of comedogenic products, and the frequency of face washing were also asked in this section. The third section dealt with details about acne. Participants were asked about their past history of acne with its severity which was used to assess whether there was an increase in acne severity or decreased/constant severity of acne. Participants with no past history of acne observed only an increase in acne. Further, family history of acne was also asked along with whether or not they were currently on prescription treatment for acne. Lastly, any other dermatoses these patients were suffering from were written down.

Acne severity was measured using the global acne grading system (GAG score)¹¹. This grading system recognizes six distinct locations for acne with a specific factor assigned to each of them. These are the forehead (I) with a factor of 2, right cheek (II) with a factor of 2, left cheek (III) with a factor of 2, nose (IV) with a factor of 1, chin (V) with a factor of 1, and chest and upper back (VI) with a factor of 3. Each lesion is also assigned a specific grade from 0 to 4: no lesion (0), comedones (1), papules (2), pustule (3), and nodule (4). The local score is calculated by multiplying the area's factor and the grade of the most severe lesion in that specific area. The global score is then obtained by the addition of the local scores of all six areas. If the global score falls between 0, 1-18, 19-30, 31-38, or >39, acne

is classified as none, mild, moderate, severe, and very severe respectively.

Data was analyzed using SPSS 26.0. t-tests and Chi square tests were applied. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered to be of significance.

Results

The mean age of the 204 participants was 23.37 ± 5.755. Other socio-demographic characteristics and data regarding mask usage and acne have been summarized in Table 1.

Most of the respondents (86.8%) were female. Surgical masks were used most commonly by 52.5% of patients, followed by KN-95 (25%), cloth masks (12.3%), and N-95 (10.3%). Most of these patients wore masks for less than 4 hours (40.7%). Only 21.6% of respondents wore their mask for more than 8 hours. The majority of patients had an oily skin type (72.1%). No significant association (p < 0.05) was found with any variable other than mask type (p = 0.001) and treatment for acne (p < 0.001).

Variable	Total (N=204)	Increase in Acne Severity (n = 106)	Decrease/no change in acne severity (n = 98)	p-value
Age, years (mean ± SD)	23.37 ± 5.755	23.65 ± 6.332	23.07 ± 5.073	0.474
Gender (%)				0.415
Male	27 (13.2)	16 (15.1)	11 (11.2)	
Female	177 (86.8)	90 (84.9)	87 (88.8)	
Marital status (%)				0.853
Unmarried	134 (65.7)	69 (65.1)	65 (66.3)	
Married	70 (34.3)	37 (34.9)	33 (33.7)	
Mask type (%)				0.001*
N-95	21 (10.3)	14 (13.2)	7 (7.1)	
KN-95	51 (25.0)	35 (33.0)	16 (16.3)	
Surgical	107 (52.5)	51 (41.8)	56 (57.1)	
Cloth	25 (12.3)	6 (5.7)	19 (19.4)	
Duration of mask (%)				0.231
Less than 4 hours	83 (40.7)	47 (44.3)	36 (36.7)	
4-8 hours	77 (37.7)	41 (38.7)	36 (36.7)	
More than 8 hours	44 (21.6)	18 (17.0)	26 (26.5)	
Frequency of changing mask daily (%)				0.201
None	66 (32.4)	40 (37.7)	26 (26.5)	
Once	119 (58.3)	58 (54.7)	61 (62.2)	
Twice or more	19 (9.3)	8 (7.5)	11 (11.2)	
Skin type (%)				0.757
Oily	147 (72.1)	74 (69.8)	73 (74.5)	
Dry	23 (11.3)	13 (12.3)	10 (10.2)	
Combination	34 (16.7)	19 (17.9)	15 (15.3)	
Use of comedogenic products (%)				0.561
Yes	77 (37.7)	38 (35.8)	39 (39.8)	
No	127 (62.3)	68 (64.2)	59 (60.2)	
Frequency of face washing (%)				0.127
1-2 times	107 (52.5)	58 (54.7)	49 (50.0)	
3-4 times	80 (39.2)	36 (34.0)	44 (44.9)	
More than 4 times	17 (8.3)	12 (11.3)	5 (5.1)	
Family history of acne (%)				0.258

Yes	104 (51.0)	50 (47.2)	54 (55.1)	
No	100 (49.0)	56 (52.8)	44 (44.9)	
Past history of acne (%)				<0.001*
Yes	145 (71.1)	47 (44.3)	98 (100.0)	
No	59 (28.9)	59 (55.7)	0 (0)	
Treatment for Acne (%)				<0.001*
Yes	76 (37.3)	20 (18.9)	56 (57.1)	
No	128 (62.7)	86 (81.1)	42 (42.9)	

Table 1

The dermatoses presented by these 204 patients were not limited to acne. Irritant contact dermatitis was found in 72 (35.5%),

allergic contact dermatitis in 102 (50.0), rosacea in 16 (7.8%), urticarial in 5 (2.5%), and folliculitis in 6 (2.9%) of these patients. This data has been plotted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Percentage of mask-wearers suffering from other dermatoses

Discussion

COVID-19, a highly contagious respiratory infection, is transmitted via aerosols released while exhaling, conversing, coughing, sneezing, and singing. These aerosols may remain suspended in the air for a long time¹². Therefore, to contain the spread of the virus, WHO recommended wearing masks soon after the COVID-19 outbreak¹³. Population masking is, in fact, one of the most effective ways of preventing COVID-19 transmission¹². It stops the uninhibited release of contaminated aerosols from an infected person into the environment - this particular mode of

prevention of virus spread is called source control which is especially important when the affected person is asymptomatic or presymptomatic - a demographic that accounts for more than 50% of disease transmissions¹⁴. Additionally, it protects the unsuspecting healthy individual from getting infected by filtering out aerosols to a great extent¹².

While mask wearing has its obvious benefits, there are some downsides to its prolonged use such as dermatoses, particularly acne¹⁵. In fact, the remarkable increase in acne following repeated masking during the pandemic birthed a new phenomenon called ‘maskne’, that is new or exacerbated acne within six weeks of wearing masks¹⁶. The most likely cause of this outbreak

is the constant friction between the face and the mask along with the alteration in pH and temperature which adversely impacts the normal skin microbiome resulting in acne^{17,18}.

Contrary to the patient population, the prevalence of maskne in healthcare workers (HCW) has been extensively researched and documented. While it is true that historically personal protective equipment (PPE) use has been restricted to HCWs, following the COVID-19 outbreak mask-wearing has been mandated for both HCWs and patients alike¹⁷. However, to the best of our knowledge, no study assessing maskne in a patient population exists in Pakistan, albeit multiple investigations have been carried out on the said association in HCWs^{8,19-21}.

Consequently, we aim to bridge this gap in the literature through our study that assesses the severity and risk factors of acne in a patient population presenting to the outpatients' department (OPD) of two tertiary care hospitals in Pakistan.

More than half of our population (n = 106) exhibited severe acne following pandemic-mandated masking, which is supported by a similar conclusion obtained by Kiely et al²². Despite most of the affected individuals being females (84.9%, n = 90), there was no statistically significant association between gender and maskne. This is contrary to the results of many other studies which demonstrate a strong relationship between the female gender and maskne^{8,22}. We believe this variation in results may be due to the remarkably fewer number of males (n = 27) as compared to females (n = 177) in our study population.

Conversely, the type of mask worn significantly affected the severity of maskne ($p < 0.05$) with surgical (41.8%), KN-95 (33.0%), and N-95 (13.2%) commonly causing severe acne whereas cloth mask (5.7%), not so much. These results are corroborated by the findings of Yaqoob et al.⁸ and Techasatian et al.²³.

Surgical masks have a loose fit that offers partial protection against pathogens. They are disposable, non-reusable, and most commonly worn by HCWs in hospital settings²⁴. However, following the masking mandate, these masks have gained popularity in the general population because they provide a greater level of comfort

than N-95s, albeit they are slightly less effective in preventing disease transmission²⁵. The fact that surgical masks comprise many layers of fibers may be the cause behind severe maskne⁸. N-95, however, is a very tightly fitting mask that is highly effective in filtering out about 95% of 0.3-micron particles. Healthcare personnel (HCP) or people tending to COVID-19 patients are recommended to wear it²⁶. The airtightness offered by the metal outline of the mask not only provides a hot and moist environment for acne-causing bacteria to proliferate but the pressure exerted by it blocks the pilosebaceous duct that may cause new acne outbreak or exacerbate pre-existing acne^{8,27}. On the contrary, cloth masks are more breathable and have the ability to absorb moisture, thereby keeping the skin dry and preventing microorganism growth¹⁸.

Duration of mask worn and frequency of changing the mask had no significant effect on maskne in our study- a finding supported by the results given by Yaqoob et al.⁸ and Kiely et al.²². However, this is an association which is slightly controversial owing to varied results in literature because according to one study, wearing PPE for more than six hours significantly increases the susceptibility to skin damage²⁸. Another study manifested the same results for a duration exceeding four hours²³. The most probable reason for our insignificant results may be the constant removal of face masks to talk, eat, or breathe properly. The same study also observed a 1.5 times increased risk of skin damage in participants who kept reusing the same mask for more than one day²³. Skin type also did not significantly impact maskne, though this is contended by two other studies stating that oily skin is more prone to maskne and acne, respectively^{8,29}.

In our study, family history of acne was not a risk factor for maskne, though a study conducted on Irish HCWs concluded otherwise²². Parallel to our study, Metin et al.³⁰ and Vural et al.³¹ observed no correlation between the frequency of face washing and maskne. Likewise, use of comedogenic products yielded no significant correlation with maskne which was also the conclusion drawn by Yaqoob et al.⁸. Lastly, despite past history of acne being a statistically significant risk factor for maskne, it is not actually a determinant because the way we

assessed the severity of acne made it impossible for a patient with no past history of acne to display any change in the severity of acne post-pandemic, thereby making the number of patients with no past history of acne and a reduced acne post-masking mandate 0.

Besides acne, prolonged masking also leads to other facial dermatoses. In our study, the most common one was allergic contact dermatitis (50.0%), followed by irritant contact dermatitis (35.3%), rosacea (7.8%), folliculitis (2.9%), and urticaria (2.5%). Contrary to our results, irritant contact dermatitis (ICD) was the most common facial dermatoses occurring due to prolonged masking in the systematic review by Yu et al.³². Allergic contact dermatitis (ACD) generally occurs less frequently than ICD³³ and is the result of thiuram found in elastic mask straps and nickel and cobalt in the metal wire of masks³⁴ - all three of which are allergens. On the other hand, parallel to our study conclusion, urticaria is not often associated with PPE³². While rosacea is not as common in our population, it shows a close association with prolonged mask wearing to the degree that mask rosacea is an emerging phenomenon³⁵. A better estimate of other dermatoses caused by facemask usage, however, could be done in studies where the inclusion criteria does not involve only acne patients.

Preventative measures

With a recent surge in COVID-19 cases and the subsequent reinstatement of the mask mandate in Pakistan, a hike in maskne prevalence is expected. Hence, it is imperative that preventative measures such as removing the mask for 15 minutes every 2 hours and cleansing the face with mild, non-comedogenic face wash³⁶ are taken by HCWs and non-HCWs alike. Moreover, when in public settings, cloth masks should be used unless the wearer is younger than 2 years or is incapable of removing the mask on their own, a recommendation supported by CDC²³. Lastly, when necessitated to use N-95, wearer should ensure moderate tightness instead of extreme and line the inside of it with a surgical mask to limit associated skin damage²³.

Limitations

While our study is one of the first to investigate the prevalence and risk factors of maskne in a patient population in Pakistan, it has a few limitations: the sample size is from only two hospitals and not large enough to be reflective of the masses. Factors that commonly affect acne like diet, genetics, and stress and hormones levels have not been accounted for. For individuals that wore two masks, the more efficient mask was chosen for data analysis. It might be possible that the other mask was worn more frequently, which might influence results. Lastly, there were patients in our population that were being treated for acne prior to the pandemic, thereby creating a possibility that the actual extent of maskne in them was reduced by the alleviating effect of the aforementioned treatment.

Conclusion

Our study suggests that acne severity increases with the use of stronger masks such as N-95 and KN-95 as compared to cloth and surgical masks. This could contribute to the development of targeted interventions aimed at minimizing the risk of acne onset and flares in the general population. Measures could be put in place by the CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention), WHO (World Health Organization) and NIH (National Institute of Health) such as the recommendation to use special non-comedogenic facewashes and have mask breaks. An appropriate mask type for each individual should also be decided. Public awareness could also help limit the side effects.

REFERENCES

1. Abid K, Abdul Bari Y, Younas M, Javaid S, Imran A. Progress of COVID-19 Epidemic in Pakistan. *Asia Pacific J Public Heal.* 2020;32:101053952092725. doi:10.1177/1010539520927259
2. Government of Pakistan. COVID-19 Health Advisory Platform by Ministry of National Health Services.
3. Rosner E. Adverse Effects of Prolonged Mask Use among Healthcare Professionals during COVID-19. *J Infect Dis Epidemiol.* 2020;6(3).

4. Kosasih LP. MASKNE: Mask-Induced Acne Flare During Coronavirus Disease-19. What is it and How to Manage it? *Open Access Maced J Med Sci*. 2020;8(T1 SE-Narrative Review Article):411-415. doi:10.3889/oamjms.2020.5388
5. Foo CCI, Goon ATJ, Leow YH, Goh CL. Adverse skin reactions to personal protective equipment against severe acute respiratory syndrome—a descriptive study in Singapore. *Contact Dermatitis*. 2006;55(5):291-294. doi:10.1111/j.1600-0536.2006.00953.x
6. Layton AM, Thiboutot D, Tan J. Reviewing the global burden of acne: how could we improve care to reduce the burden? *Br J Dermatol*. 2021;184(2):219-225. doi:10.1111/bjd.19477
7. Katta R, Desai SP. Diet and dermatology: the role of dietary intervention in skin disease. *J Clin Aesthet Dermatol*. 2014;7(7):46-51. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25053983>
8. Yaqoob S, Saleem A, Jarullah FA, Asif A, Essar MY, Emad S. Association of Acne with Face Mask in Healthcare Workers Amidst the COVID-19 Outbreak in Karachi, Pakistan. *Clin Cosmet Investig Dermatol*. 2021;14:1427-1433. doi:10.2147/CCID.S333221
9. Chughtai AA, Seale H, Macintyre CR. Effectiveness of Cloth Masks for Protection Against Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2. *Emerg Infect Dis*. 2020;26(10). doi:10.3201/eid2610.200948
10. Chazelet S, Pacault S. Efficiency of Community Face Coverings and Surgical Masks to Limit the Spread of Aerosol. *Ann Work Expo Heal*. 2022;66(4):495-509. doi:10.1093/annweh/wxab089
11. Doshi A, Zaheer A, Stiller MJ. A comparison of current acne grading systems and proposal of a novel system. *Int J Dermatol*. 1997;36(6):416-418. doi:10.1046/j.1365-4362.1997.00099.x
12. Brooks JT, Butler JC. Effectiveness of Mask Wearing to Control Community Spread of SARS-CoV-2. *JAMA*. 2021;325(10):998-999. doi:10.1001/jama.2021.1505
13. When and how to use masks. Accessed August 2, 2022. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/advice-for-public/when-and-how-to-use-masks>
14. Johansson MA, Quandelacy TM, Kada S, et al. SARS-CoV-2 Transmission From People Without COVID-19 Symptoms. *JAMA Netw open*. 2021;4(1):e2035057. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.35057
15. Singh M, Pawar M, Bothra A, et al. Personal protective equipment induced facial dermatoses in healthcare workers managing Coronavirus disease 2019. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2020;34(8):e378-e380. doi:10.1111/jdv.16628
16. Teo WL. Diagnostic and management considerations for “maskne” in the era of COVID-19. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2021;84(2):520-521. doi:10.1016/j.jaad.2020.09.063
17. Villani A, Fabbrocini G, Annunziata MC, Potestio L. Maskne prevalence and risk factors during the COVID-19 pandemic. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. Published online May 2022. doi:10.1111/jdv.18248
18. Teo WL. The “Maskne” microbiome - pathophysiology and therapeutics. *Int J Dermatol*. 2021;60(7):799-809. doi:10.1111/ijd.15425
19. Zaib, Naqvi F, Inayat S, et al. Cutaneous impact of surgical mask versus N 95 mask during covid-19 pandemic: Incidence of dermatological side effects and response of topical methylprednisolone aceponate (MPA) treatment to associated contact dermatitis. *J Pakistan Assoc Dermatologists*. 2020;30(4):650-655.

20. Hayat W, Malik LM, Mukhtar R, Khan MQ, Saeed A, Rashid T. 'MASKNE' (MASK INDUCED ACNE) IN HEALTH CARE PROFESSIONALS OF TERTIARY CARE HOSPITALS OF LAHORE DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC. *Pakistan Postgrad Med J*. 2020;31(2):61-65.
21. Bashir S. Skin related health issues among health care workers due to utilizing of personal protective equipment during COVID-19 pandemic in Pakistan. *Qeios*. doi:10.32388/XMJXCE
22. Kiely LF, O'Connor C, O'Briain G, O'Briain C, Gallagher J, Bourke JF. Maskne prevalence and associated factors in Irish healthcare workers during the COVID-19 pandemic. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venerol*. 2022;36(7):e506-e508. doi:10.1111/jdv.18054
23. Techasatian L, Lebsing S, Uppala R, et al. The Effects of the Face Mask on the Skin Underneath: A Prospective Survey During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *J Prim Care Community Health*. 2020;11:2150132720966167. doi:10.1177/2150132720966167
24. N95 Respirators, Surgical Masks, Face Masks, and Barrier Face Coverings | FDA. Accessed August 2, 2022. <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/personal-protective-equipment-infection-control/n95-respirators-surgical-masks-face-masks-and-barrier-face-coverings>
25. Worby CJ, Chang HH. Face mask use in the general population and optimal resource allocation during the COVID-19 pandemic. *medRxiv Prepr Serv Heal Sci*. Published online April 2020. doi:10.1101/2020.04.04.20052696
26. Personal Protective Equipment: Questions and Answers | CDC. Accessed August 2, 2022. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/hcp/respirator-use-faq.html>
27. Malik LM, Ilyas S, Hayat W, Mukhtar R, Rashid S, Rashid T. Skin Manifestations Associated with Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) in Health Care Professionals during COVID 19 Pandemic. *Esculapio*. 2020;16(1):61-65.
28. Lan J, Song Z, Miao X, et al. Skin damage among health care workers managing coronavirus disease-2019. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2020;82(5):1215-1216. doi:10.1016/j.jaad.2020.03.014
29. Heng AHS, Chew FT. Systematic review of the epidemiology of acne vulgaris. *Sci Rep*. 2020;10(1):5754. doi:10.1038/s41598-020-62715-3
30. Metin N, Turan Ç, Utlu Z. Changes in dermatological complaints among healthcare professionals during the COVID-19 outbreak in Turkey. *Acta dermatovenerologica Alpina, Pannonica, Adriat*. 2020;29(3):115-122.
31. Tunçer Vural A. The development of acne vulgaris due to face masks during the pandemic, risk awareness and attitudes of a group of university students. *J Cosmet Dermatol*. Published online May 2022. doi:10.1111/jocd.15120
32. Yu J, Chen JK, Mowad CM, et al. Occupational dermatitis to facial personal protective equipment in health care workers: A systematic review. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2021;84(2):486-494. doi:10.1016/j.jaad.2020.09.074
33. Sasseville D. Occupational contact dermatitis. *Allergy, asthma, Clin Immunol Off J Can Soc Allergy Clin Immunol*. 2008;4(2):59-65. doi:10.1186/1710-1492-4-2-59
34. Warshaw EM, Schlarbaum JP, Silverberg JI, et al. Safety equipment: When protection becomes a problem. *Contact Dermatitis*. 2019;81(2):130-132. doi:10.1111/cod.13254

35. Damiani G, Gironi LC, Grada A, et al. COVID-19 related masks increase severity of both acne (maskne) and rosacea (mask rosacea): Multi-center, real-life, telemedical, and observational prospective study. *Dermatol Ther.* 2021;34(2):e14848.
doi:10.1111/dth.14848
36. Desai SR, Kovarik C, Brod B, et al. COVID-19 and personal protective equipment: Treatment and prevention of skin conditions related to the occupational use of personal protective equipment. *J Am Acad Dermatol.* 2020;83(2):675-677.
doi:10.1016/j.jaad.2020.05.032

